

NEWSLETTER

Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Centre

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July - December 2023

Dear Alumni,
this newsletter and the next one, due in spring 2024, bracket a major transition for our Center. The thematic focus is now clearly shifting to aspects of tumor biology and immunology, to create an even stronger base for joint grants and projects. On this occasion we highlight the past and the future of our Center. In the present edition, founding member Albert Duschl recalls some facets about the history of our Center (of which you are a part) and in the next edition, our new speaker Jutta Horejs-Höck will explain future goals and strategies. In addition, we introduce the group of Dirk Schmidt-Arras, which works on tumor immunology.

- ❖ Our Center: Past, Presence and Future. Part I
- ❖ Schmidt-Arras Lab: Tumour Immunology Group

Enjoy reading!

Our Center: Past, Present and Future

Part I

Background story

In the beginning, there was the law.

Strong first paragraph, hm?

The law was in this case the Universitätsgesetz 2002 (university law, UG), which was phased in starting 2002 and took full effect on 1. 1. 2004. It replaced the UOG 1993, which until then regulated the Austrian universities. A crucial difference between the two laws was, that with the UG the universities became full legal bodies, while until then they had largely been governed by the Ministry. Freedom at last!

Now, before we go overboard, let's not forget that the budget still comes from the Ministry. The amount is negotiated, and the negotiations can get quite heated, speaking from experience, but in the end, they have the money, and we need it, so the Ministry maintains a strong position. It has also, by law, an oversight function. It cannot, however, give orders. The universities have now a substantial independence, which includes the internal organization: Each university can decide on an internal structure.

Our Center owes its existence to § 13 (2) of the UG¹, which stipulates that universities have to define their specific profile and, in this context, also their special research focus areas. The University of Salzburg has used the freedom given by the UG for sweeping reforms and this included a clear definition of scientific priority areas. This is the origin of our Center.

So, why are we called a Schwerpunkt, which we usually translate as “priority area” or as “excellence center”? Neither is really satisfactory: Nobody outside of Salzburg knows what a priority area is, and it is not advisable to call yourself excellent (let other people do that). Why “Schwerpunkt” and not “Center”?

¹ § 13. (1) Die Leistungsvereinbarung ist ein öffentlich-rechtlicher Vertrag. Sie ist zwischen den einzelnen Universitäten und dem Bund im Rahmen der Gesetze für jeweils drei Jahre abzuschließen. (2) Inhalt der Leistungsvereinbarung ist insbesondere: 1. die von der Universität zu erbringenden Leistungen, die entsprechend den Zielen, leitenden Grundsätzen und Aufgaben der Universität in folgenden Bereichen festzulegen sind: a) strategische Ziele, Profilbildung, Universitäts- und Personalentwicklung; Die langfristigen und die innerhalb der Leistungsvereinbarungsperiode zu erreichenden Ziele sind festzulegen. Die Universität hat ihre besonderen Schwerpunkte und Stärken und den daraus abgeleiteten und zur Zielerreichung vorgesehenen Ressourceneinsatz bekannt zu geben. Es ist anzugeben, welche Fördermaßnahmen und Anreize zur Erreichung der Ziele in der Personalentwicklung erforderlich sind und welche Beiträge die Angehörigen der Universität leisten sollen.
UG, current version

Because it reflects the phrasing of the UG and clearly answers to the demand laid down in § 13 (2). We are now a bit stuck with it, since the university applied the term “Center” to another type of organization unit, which is smaller, much narrower in focus, and can basically rest on one person, which would be impossible for a Schwerpunkt. The University has at present 9 centers of this smaller type² and 3 Schwerpunkte³. At some point we have to deal with the name, an issue that will be addressed extensively in part II. For now, we are focusing on the historical background, shall call the “Schwerpunkte” Centers, and to hell with it.

Einladung
zur außerordentlichen Sitzung des Senates

Zeit: Dienstag, 2. Juli 2002, 9.15 Uhr
Ort: Sitzungssaal des Senates, Kapitelgasse 4, 1. Stock

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**Entscheidung des Senates
über die Schwerpunktsetzungen der Universität Salzburg
am Dienstag, 2. Juli 2002**

Im Anschluss an die ausführlichen Diskussionen während der vergangenen Monate sowie mit Bezug auf die eingelangten Gutachten zu den fünf vorgelegten Schwerpunktkonzepten hat der Senat nach ausführlichen Beratungen auf Vorschlag des Rektors folgende Entscheidungen getroffen:

1. Es wird **definitiv beschlossen**, im Sinne der erfolgten Definition von "universitärem Schwerpunkt" sowie im Hinblick auf die aufgestellten Kriterien des damit verbundenen Anforderungsprofils, aber auch unter Bedachtnahme der gegebenen Situation des Universitätsstandortes Salzburg und der geplanten universitären Bauprojekte sowohl den Schwerpunkt *Wissenschaft und Kunst - Zusammenarbeit der Salzburger Universitäten* als auch den Schwerpunkt *Biowissenschaften und Gesundheit* einzurichten.

Getting it started

Our official history begins essentially twice: First on 2. 7. 2002, when the Senate approved the proposal of the Rector to install our Center⁴ along with three others, and secondly on 1. 1. 2004, when the new structure of the University fully went into force. After the reform, there were actually fewer internal organization units than before, since for example the previous institutes were transformed into departments, which were usually bigger, so the number was cut nearly

by half⁵. However, there were also new units, and among them 4 large research centers:

- Biosciences and Health (this is us)
- Information and Communication Technology & Society
- Law, business and working environment
- Science and arts

You will notice that we are the only one of these units that still operates as a Center. We were from the beginning the largest of the Centers and we are also the oldest. Consider the strong fluctuation: Centers get evaluated by a panel of external experts every 5 years and this can lead to demotion, as can a failure to fulfill the expectations due to such a prominent unit, or a re-focusing of overall strategies. We had to prove again and again that we are really an outstanding research cluster

² <https://www.plus.ac.at/the-university-of-salzburg/centres/?lang=en>

³ <https://www.plus.ac.at/the-university-of-salzburg/focus-areas/?lang=en&svs=35>

⁴ And there was substantial opposition, especially since our Center was considered to be too expensive. Well, we are representing experimental disciplines. Some colleagues in other faculties get by with a laptop and a library pass, but we don't.

⁵ Fun fact: Numerous people have predicted at that time the end of the world if the institutes were abolished. Still waiting for it.

within the university. Our last report, for the evaluation in 2021, gave impressive numbers and we are happy to repeat our favorite one: With only 12 working groups, we have acquired in 2016-2020 a total of € 15.8 Mio in new external grants, which is 14.6% of the grant income of the University in that period. And that is the reason why we are a Center.

Our unofficial history begins in early 2002, more than 20 years ago, when the University invited applications to become one of the new Centers. Seven groups got together to develop plans for such a Center, which brought together allergy research (Gernot Achatz, Albert Duschl, Fatima Ferreira, Gerhard Obermeyer, Josef Thalhamer), Genomics (Annemarie Frischaut) and Bioinformatics (Manfred Sippl). One challenge was to find ways to really enhance cooperation between the different groups and areas. The Center has genuinely accomplished that, which is an important reason for our success. If you are just in there to get some money, the whole construct quickly falls apart.

Another challenge arose after our application had been approved and the Center was established: The concept was fully up to date when we wrote it, but science is about innovation. It is necessary to constantly re-invent yourself. We are grateful to the University that in recruitments, it was continuously possible to deposit our wishes on how the Center could benefit by acquiring new knowledge, methods and competences that would be synergistic to the existing team. The University development plan of 2004 already indicated that a fourth area was to be established within the Center, which was protein research. Additions were always carefully planned to enable synergies with the existing groups. This one required even a new building, the one in the Billrothstraße, opened in 2005 – a very substantial support for us! Other extensions included several new groups established in

Biology, two groups from Materials Sciences, which left the Center in 2022, and by now one group in Computer Sciences, so we are still present in the Itzling Campus.

Evolution of the Center happened not only through additions, but also through gradual re-focusing, often driven by the opportunities for cooperation within the Center, which is thus also a platform to foster joint projects. Groups have shifted their focus to profit from synergies within the Center.

The founding group of allergy researchers

What's in a name?

Our first name was Bioscience and Health, which readily covered all areas and was in line with the sweeping names for organization units preferred by the University at that time. Such names tended to become over times narrower and narrower, to give a better definition of what is really happening⁶. The re-naming of Biosciences and Health was, however, prompted by the Ministry, which wanted a more specific name and rejected our own proposals for a new name. To be honest, Allergy Cancer BioNano was a compromise that we did not actually want⁷.

⁶ Interestingly, there is a counter-move. The University has recently established four "guiding principles", which are Art in Context, Digital Life, Development & Sustainability and Health & Mind. Both general and specific names have their benefits.

⁷ One reason was that the first Google hits for ACBN led to the African Christian Broadcasting Network. Findability in the internet is really important.

The BioNano part was a new development that also brought in the groups from Materials Sciences. Cancer, on the other hand, was initially based on the genomics area formerly highlighted. More groups could contribute to research on cancer then to genomics, so this one became an anchor of the Center. The other anchor was and is immunology, as allergy research was widened into diverse aspects of immunity.

The re-invention goes on and on as science develops and as groups are changed. At the time this newsletter is published, Fatima Ferreira will be the only one of the original founders that is still active in the Center, and she retires in 2024. The generational change will be completed by then. This also implies that allergy, long our hallmark, will no longer be in focus. BioNano is phased out with the retirement of Albert Duschl in 2023. Immunology and Cancer will be the main issues in the future, especially concerning their interaction. With 2024, there will be a new name that reflects this, which is Center for Tumor Biology and Immunology, CTBI. Part II of this article will tell you about our strategy for the future and will also explain how we can find our niche in this extremely competitive area.

How we work

The formula is

(Strong Groups + Interest in Cooperation) x Relevant Methods = Successful Joint Projects & Papers

See? It 's quite simple. Weak groups cooperating does not make the science stronger, strong groups failing to cooperate cannot gain

synergy benefits. And if your methods are outdated, even great ideas will have a hard time getting realized.

The hierarchy is pretty flat. There is one speaker⁸ and there is the assembly of PIs, which meets whenever necessary. In the last few years, we also have also established monthly online faculty meetings, where the faculty is defined as anybody with a doctoral degree working in one of the member groups. And of course, the Center really needs a secretary. Since the retirement of Elisabeth Eppacher, this is Bernadette Kaufmann.

Why PhD students are so important to us

Well, for one thing, they do a substantial amount of the work, right? In addition, joint training for PhD students is by now standard⁹, so one person has close ties to different groups, which is a strong stimulus for cooperation. When the group members are in good contact, joint activities emerge as a matter of course. This bottom-up approach is usually even more effective than the discussions between group leaders, so well done, folks.

PhD students are often very good networkers and this becomes even more efficient when they are in a doctoral program together with others. This can be a program that includes international locations, like the ITN projects of the European Union. Or they can be localized in one site, with national funding. The single most important project in the history of the Center was the FWF-funded doctoral school Immunity in Cancer and Allergy (ICA), which included numerous groups from the Center. We got funded for 12 years, the absolute maximum, so we received three prolongations and this was anything but given: The FWF is much inclined to terminate ongoing projects, to free up money for new ones.

Doctoral schools provide not only connections, but also a structured training program for the fellows. This clearly improved the training in scientific issues, but even more so in accessory skills like scientific writing or presenting. We have at the end of every semester our doctoral seminar where, for two days, PhD students plus some senior experts give talks. The average (!) level of the PhD talks from our own students is extremely high¹⁰, while external students are, on average, at a lower skill level. So, it's the training all right.

ICA has ended, but left a strong legacy. Our own PhD training program is substantially copied from the ICA program, so the quality was

⁸ Until 2018 this was Josef Thalhamer, since then Albert Duschl, and after his retirement in 2023, Jutta Horejs-Höck.

⁹ And a good thing this is. When I did my PhD, my supervisor was fully absent for nearly a year, due to very serious health problems. There was no Assistant in the group and nobody stepped in to take care of the PhD students. That would be impossible today.

¹⁰ Much better than mine at that stage.

maintained. The Faculty and the University have also moved to imitate parts of this best-practice example, so the original intention of the FWF was met. The FWF installed a program for doctoral schools to improve the PhD training in Austrian universities and thus the quality of Austrian research. This plan has worked.

The sad news is that the FWF has accordingly abolished the original doctoral schools program and new funding schemes for PhD programs are on a much more modest level, especially in terms of financing. Nevertheless, groups from the Center are going for the new funding schemes, so we hope to acquire some FWF money specifically for PhD training.

UNIVERSITÄT SALZBURG

Research Topics at the Department of Molecular Biology

Focus Area "Allergy-Cancer-BioNano Research Centre – ACBN"

ACBN was established by the Paris-Lodron-University of Salzburg in 2015 out of the original priority program "BioScience and Health" which had been founded in 2003. The declared aims of the program are performance of **excellent basic science and translational research** with high international visibility and recognition. Ten working groups of the Department as well as two more of the Chemistry and Physics of Materials Department investigate the molecular and cellular basis of different diseases and disease mechanisms.

Current research collaborations focus on the topics **allergy, immunology, cancer research, bio-nano interaction, and structural biology**. The basic research performed in ACBN should help to **better understand the molecular and cellular basis of diseases such as cancer or allergy**, in order to develop better tools for their diagnosis and therapeutic treatment. Synergistic use of knowledge, expertise, competence, and infrastructure facilitates multidisciplinary approaches to scientific problems and ideas, and leads to a constructive and inspiring working environment. This also impacts our young scientists, who thus derive very significant **benefits from the expertise, research tools, and infrastructure available in the priority program**, thus providing a solid and real-life oriented basis for the state-of-the-art education of students in the different study programs of biology at the University.

Another important aspect of the continuous development of the focus area is the preparation and **founding of larger research structures**. ACBN members were successful in recruiting third party funding for individual projects but also in the establishment of national and international large-scale projects, such as Christian Doppler Laboratories, joint projects within European Framework Programs, and national and international training networks/doctoral colleges. Recently, members of ACBN founded the "Cancer Cluster Salzburg – CCS", a collaboration network of basic scientists and clinicians with a unique focus on tumor microenvironment and tumor stem cells.

Up to the present time, ACBN expanded step-by-step and developed a clear and distinct research profile, thus being a good example of the successful implementation of focus areas by the University of Salzburg.

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Albert Duschl

Outlook

There isn't any outlook in this text. It's part one of two, remember? The outlook will be included in part 2, published in the next edition. In the meantime, have fun and enjoy a successful career!

Schmidt-Arras Lab: Tumour Immunology Group

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Very often patients present at advanced stages of disease with tumour cell dissemination at distant organ sites, a process called metastasis. Despite advances in the field, for many tumour entities an efficient curative therapy is still lacking. This is the motivation of the tumour immunology group (TIG) to understand the cellular and molecular mechanisms that create a micro-environment in which a tumour can grow and escape an anti-tumour immune response. We aim to tackle this unsolved question by applying different and novel mouse models, state-of-the-art biochemical, cell biological, immunological and bioinformatic methods. We are always eager to expand our methodological repertoire and to perform our research in an interdisciplinary and cooperative way.

Main research areas

Signalling of IL-6 family cytokines in inflammation and tumour formation

The family of interleukin 6 (IL-6) cytokines has eleven members and pleiotropic functions within the body. All family members share the same signal transducing subunit GP130 (Figure 1A). While GP130 is ubiquitously expressed, expression of IL-6 receptor α (IL-6RA) is limited to certain cell types. However, a soluble form of IL-6RA (sIL-6RA) can be generated by limited proteolysis, involving in particular members of the ADAM protease family. The complex of IL-6 and sIL-6RA can now engage a GP130 homodimer and induce signalling in cells that do not express IL-6RA (Figure 1B). This process is called IL-6 trans-signalling. IL-6 trans-signalling can be specifically blocked by a recombinant dimerized form of soluble GP130 (sGP130, Olamkcept, Figure 1B).

We have previously shown that IL-6 trans-signalling emanating from myeloid cells in the tumour micro-environment promotes hepatic and colorectal tumour formation (Bergmann et al. *Hepatology* 2017, Schmidt et al. *J Exp Med* 2018) and that IL-6 trans-signalling in hepatic progenitor cells promotes mixed hepatocellular-cholangiocarcinoma (Rosenberg et al. *J Hepatol* 2022).

In order to assess a cell type-specific role of IL-6/GP130 (trans-) signalling, we developed a mouse model with a synthetic cytokine receptor that allows to induce IL-6/GP130 activation in a cell-autonomous and ligand-independent manner (Schumacher et al. *J Hepatol* 2020, Heinig et al. *J Immunol* 2023). We use this model to address cell type-specificity of IL-6 signalling and its impact on hepatic inflammation, such as auto-immune cholangitis and tumour formation. This will help us in the future to design novel therapeutic approaches to cell type-specifically inhibit pro-inflammatory and tumour-

promoting IL-6 signalling without compromising beneficial effects of IL-6 signalling. Furthermore, we use this model to investigate how GP130 signalling in hepatocytes and concomitantly induced acute-phase proteins promote primary tumour growth and liver metastasis. In this project we are cooperating with regional (Nadja Zaborsky, Richard Greil SALK/LIMCR Salzburg) and external partners (Dorothee Schwinge, University Hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf; University Hospital Kiel; Jürgen Scheller, University of Düsseldorf). In cooperation with Alexander Egle (SALK/LIMCR Salzburg) we will further use these mice and IL-6-specific tools in a project that investigates how the different IL-6/GP130 signalling modes nourish malignant B-cells in chronic lymphocytic leukaemia.

In the recent years, gain- and loss-of-function mutations of GP130 have been discovered. In close collaboration with Holm Uhlig (University of Oxford) we have characterised several patient-derived loss-of-function mutations, including the use of CRISPR-mediated knock-in mice (Chen et al. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2021, Schwerd et al. *Bone Res* 2020). Interestingly, while some of these mutations cause Hyper IgE-syndrome, others are linked to a more severe disease phenotype (Figure 1C). In continuation of this collaboration we are seeking to understand from these and novel mutations, how trafficking and signalling of GP130, including cytokine selectivity is regulated on a molecular/structural level and how this affects pathology.

IL-6/GP130 signaling in inflammation and tumour formation

Cellular activities within healthy tissues are regulated by extracellular signalling molecules. They are often originating from neighbouring cells, either of the same or a different cell type (juxtacrine signalling), or from more distant cells in the tissue (paracrine signalling). Tumours are composed not only of tumour cells (TCs) but also contain other cell types such as immune and stromal cells that form a tumour niche. Thus, tumours are complex tissue-like cellular assemblies with varying

heterogeneity. As in healthy tissues, the cellular interplay and the fate of TCs in these complex assemblies is regulated by juxta- and paracrine signals.

In contrast to long ranging endocrine signals, juxta- and paracrine signals act on a short distance. While juxtacrine signals are induced by membrane-bound ligands that act only on juxtaposed cells, paracrine signals are soluble and are thought to act on cells within a range of a few cell layers (Figure 2). Multiple ligands are synthesized as membrane-bound ligands. Their extracellular part can act as paracrine signal upon release by limited proteolysis, a process termed “shedding”. Therefore, proteolytic enzymes, termed “sheddasess” not only regulate the onset of signalling but also determine the range and the quality of intercellular signalling (Figure 2). Members of the a disintegrin and metalloprotease (ADAM) family are major mediators of shedding.

In the TIG we aim at understanding how members of the ADAM family and the release of their substrates is regulated on a molecular level and how this effects cellular networks in particular in the immune micro-environment of chronic inflammation and malignant disease. Together with colleagues at PLUS (Iris Gratz, Nikolaus Fortelny, Peter Lackner, Markus Wiederstein) and external partners (Monika Ettinger, University hospital Linz) we are currently investigating the role of the family member ADAM17 for chronic inflammation and the underlying molecular basis, including the analysis of patient-derived ADAM17 mutants.

We have previously shown a critical role for ADAM17 in the tumour micro-environment on primary colorectal tumour growth (Schmidt et al, *J Exp Med* 2018) and metastasis to the lung (Bolik et al, *J Exp Med* 2022). In our group we continue on this line of research and systematically investigate the cell type-specific role of ADAM17 in the tumour immune micro-environment of chronic lymphocytic leukaemia and mamma carcinoma. In this project we are collaborating with regional (Nadja Zaborsky, LIMCR Salzburg, Richard Greil, Roland Reitsamer, SALK Salzburg) and external (Dirk Bauerschlag, University hospital Kiel, Achim Krüger, Technical University München) partners.

Micro-environmental ADAM proteases as key regulators of inflammation, tumour growth and metastasis

The research group

In the tumour immunology group we are keen to create an open, interactive and creative environment to enable the creation of novel and crazy ideas to break our scientific and methodological boundaries. In regular lab meetings and personal discussions we discuss problems and progress of every member and collectively design novel experimental strategies. We set high value on the intrinsic motivation of every group member and its individual creativity, and to be on par with everyone. In order to strengthen the team spirit and to mutually learn from each other, the group organises social events outside the laboratory. Via the CIVIS European University Alliance (www.civis.eu) we contribute to medical biology education and research interaction in Europe. We are proud of already having been the host laboratory for several Erasmus+ students from three different European countries.

With a piece of humour, personal engagement and scientific enthusiasm we aim to create a strong team spirit.

Dirk Schmidt-Arras

Dirk Schmidt-Arras (principal investigator) studied Biochemistry and Molecular Biology at the Universities of Bayreuth and Jena. In 2002 he obtained his Diploma degree from the University of Jena. He then continued at the University Jena in the laboratory of Prof. Frank Böhmer at the Institute of Molecular Cell Biology to work on the receptor tyrosine kinase FLT3 in the context of acute myeloid leukemia (AML), where he received his PhD in 2007. As an INSERM postdoctoral fellow he joined the laboratory of Dr. Gerald Spaeth at the Institut Pasteur in Paris to pursue studies on mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) in *Leishmania* parasites where he was also part of the international FP7-funded “LeishDrug” consortium. In 2010 he joined the Institute of Biochemistry at the University of Kiel to work as an independent group leader. Here he established his research focus on IL-6 family cytokine and ADAM metalloproteases. In 2014 he became project leader in the Collaborative Research Center SFB841 on liver

inflammation. In the same year he also became full member of the Cluster of Excellence “Inflammation at Interfaces” at the University of Kiel, the University Priority Area “Kiel Life Science” and the “Kiel Oncology Network”. In 2017 he obtained the lecturer qualification and the *Venia Legendi* in the subject “Biochemistry” at the University of Kiel.

In 2021 he joined the Paris-Lodron University of Salzburg in August 2021 as Assistant Professor to head the Tumor Immunology Group at the Department of Life Sciences and Medical Biology. In 2022 he became deputy speaker for the department’s structured PhD education program “Doctorate School PLUS Biomolecules in Health and Disease”. In 2023 his group joined the University’s Research Priority Area ACBN and Dirk was elected as deputy speaker of the focus area. Since 2022 Dirk acts as a CIVIS facilitator for the topics “Cancer, Immunology” within the CIVIS hub “Health”, involved in education. He is also a co-initiator of a CIVIS Spatial Biology Network.

Dirk has a long-standing teaching experience in Biochemistry, Molecular Biology, Immunology and Tumor Biology and loves to share his passion for science and research. Dirk also recently engaged in science communication by initiating a collaboration between ACBN and Salzburg’s renowned Museum of Natural Sciences (“Haus der Natur”).

Freia Krause

Freia Krause (PhD student) is a founding member of the Tumour Immunology Group at PLUS and a long time member of our research group. She obtained her master’s degree in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology in 2021 at the University of Kiel. Freia already joined our group in 2017, at that time still at the University of Kiel. Albeit at the beginning of her research career, she is already experienced and is first author (Schwerd*, Krause* et al., *Bone Res* 2020) and co-author (Bolik, Krause et al. *J Exp Med* 2021; Chen,...Krause et al., *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2021) of several high-impact publications of the group. In 2021 she embarked as a PhD student in our group to characterise the hepatic tumour niche. Beyond her own scientific project, Freia pioneers in establishing novel methodology in the laboratory.

Elena Voglas

Elena Voglas (technician) joined the laboratory in 2022 as a highly experienced half-time lab technician. After studies of medicine and genetics/biotechnology, she obtained her bachelor’s degree in genetics/biotechnology in 2004 at the University of Salzburg. Since 2005 she works as a half-time lab technician in the group of Raimund Tenhaken, Plant Physiology, University of Salzburg. Elena has strong experience in molecular biology techniques, a high sense of responsibility and organisation but is also pioneering in the establishment of novel techniques. She largely contributes to practical student education and is a linking hub for students, sales representatives, technical support and other groups within the university. Elena is also essential in teaching students in laboratory courses and during their Bachelor and Master’s thesis.

Luisa Conrady

Birgit Halwachs

Luisa Conrady (technician, master student) joined the laboratory in 2021 as a student assistant. Since 2022 she is employed as half-time technician. Luisa studied Special Needs Pedagogy and Biology and obtained her Bachelor’s degree in Biology in 2021 at the University of Biology. She then embarked in the Master Program Medical Biology at the University of Salzburg. Since 2023 she is performing her master thesis on immunological functions of ADAM17 in the skin in her ‘spare time’ in our group.

Birgit Halwachs (master student) joined the group in 2022. Birgit studied Medical Biology at the University of Salzburg and obtained her Bachelor’s degree in 2022. She then embarked in the Master Program Medical Biology at the University of Salzburg and is currently performing her Master thesis in our group investigating the impact of hepatic GP130 signalling and acute-phase proteins on liver metastasis. Beside her Master thesis project, Birgit is employed as student assistant to investigate patient-derived ADAM17 mutations. Birgit is our only Austrian National Team member and World Champion.

So, farewell for now from the Center and also from Albert, who is enjoying his retirement.

**Look forward to future news,
enjoy your life and have a successful career!**

Image references:

Paris-Lodron-University of Salzburg, Luigi Caputo, ACBN, Schmidt-Arras Lab

Legal notice:

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Allergy Cancer BioNano

Research Centre

ACBN